

Graphic representation of dataset for the project "IRI-model performance evaluation for the Mexican region"

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Abstract: Here, we illustrate the modeling and experimental results for vertical Total Electron Content (TEC) over Mexico during the five-year period 2018-2022. The results were obtained for the UCOE GNSS receiver station (geographic coordinates: 19.6°N; 101.68°W). The calculations were made each two hours during the whole period under considerations. The modeling results were obtained using the "International Reference Ionosphere (IRI)" model, which is an empirical climatological model based on ground and space observations of the ionosphere [Bilitza et al., 2022].

Data Availability Statement: This work is based on GPS data from UCOE station provided by the TLALOCNet network of GNSS receivers ((<http://tlalocnet.udg.mx>, and <http://132.248.208.61> last accessed on 25 December 2022).

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(1) daily values IRI-2016 and observations.
2018

2022

(2) daily values IRI-Plas and observations.

2018

2019

